

Sample Name: PET UV 5-10 μm

Material: Polyethylene terephthalate

Size: 5-10 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 11,24 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $1,8 \times 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- 7097 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ (PET) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling or aging observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
14,85	6,13	1,67	0,74	0,51	11,24	1.8×10^{11}	7097

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$	99,93
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	134
S	12
Cl	335
K	14
Ca	4
Ti	1
Cr	19
Fe	76
Ni	10
Cu	6
Zn	2
Mo	1
Pb	1

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (*provided by TNO*)

Not available